

July 31, 2018

Big Data Analytics, Contexts of Oral Literature and Decision Making Processes: Rethinking Software Archiving In Post-Colonial Digital Humanities

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Abstract

This paper advances the hypothesis that big data analytics has an enormous value that can be utilized not only for various purposes like decision making for political gains and market profit but also for the creation of a database for literary studies and ethnicity/cultural preservation. However, it maintains that the coding methodology in the general application of big data analytics to industry and business is not configured in the same way as in the conservation of culture. While machines can perform certain tasks more efficiently than humans, machines cannot effectively handle the humanistic environments of projects like software archiving of continental oral literature. Consequently, the 'traditional way' of doing things that have survived and is still active based on the coding methodology in computerization of big data should be adapted in the future in order to efficiently handle the tacit components of big data in oral literary archiving. It argues that the software digitization model needs to be very sensitive to the implicit contexts of application in the oral continental discourse, by handling not only the 'correlative' but also the 'causative' in the continuum where 'code' meets with the discursivity of the environment. .

Keywords

Big data analytics, oral literature and culture, cognitive and intensive contexts, decision making, email testing, Dicode project, social media

1.0 Introduction

Drawing insights from the critical social paradigms of software archiving, this paper re-thinks the methodological issue of *coding* in computer-assisted big data analytics by showing how *coding* as a correlation-causation continuum in cognitively intensive contexts such as oral literary culture, needs to take into account not only the textual, but also the para-textual, vocal, and kinesic elements of data construction. The analysis of oral data cannot be disembedded from the process of interviewing informants, making decisions about what, where, how to collect, transcription, translation, exploitation, etc. The purpose is to contribute to the debate on coding, which has often been reduced to technical categorizations in software archiving. It asks the simple question: what is coding and how does it take form in the digital technologies when a complex domain of society such as the oral humanities in Africa (or elsewhere) has to be archived? From the definitional perspective, the rationalizing belief in digital technologies is that coding has to do with mathematics and algorithms. On the other hand, the thinking in the humanities is that coding is not a narrowly mechanical process but a greater achievement that has to do with grasping the *essentialism* of information and communication. Thus, there is a clear dichotomy between coding in quantitative and qualitative contexts of research. But this paper argues that the two paradigms are interdependent rather than exclusive to each other and the critical paradigm of the humanities is necessary to support the long term sustainability of the digital technologies and quantitative paradigm.

This paper is premised on the hypothesis that the coding process of big data analytics in the computer software archiving of oral literature does not function in an autonomous, self-contained and auto-regulating vacuum, but is a *potentially* social and cultural and linguistic construction. Therefore, it proposes to investigate how coding in the expanded *contexts* of orality. Data is obtained from many sources with a low signal-to-noise ratio for solving problems. The variance of data in terms of importance, subjectivity, scope, etc, is a result of the fact that sources are founded on shifting individual opinions, approximations, practices that are more or less acceptable, scientific measurements and results that are more or less trusted. The further questions are: can the

July 31, 2018

collector of data share cognition on how to leverage analytics from huge datasets of orality in an environment of competitive advantage? In this epoch of market volatility generating transactional situational happenstances, how can managers of data take cognizance of the synergies in the big data environment of orality marked by huge size, sharper skill, greater scope and higher speed (the 4Ss)? This paper is significant because it goes beyond the correlative *product* of collected data to investigate the causative *processes* of big data collection. Data analysis is embedded in research methods because it is only when it is clear how an oral *text* stands in relation to its audience *performance* and when its performance is related to its oral tradition, that the real task of analysis of data content can start. Thus, the yawning gap between software data analysis as a technological activity and collection of data as a cognitive and attitudinal process needs to be filled in the future.

2.0 Background literature

The literature shows that big data analytics has prioritized chiefly quantitative outcomes in the exploitation of data collection. The insurance industry, for example, leverages big data analytics extensively. The value of the insurance company in 2013 was evaluated by the India Brand Equity Foundation at 66 billion USD. 30% of India's advertizing digital market is represented by search advertizing, according to reports of the Internet and Mobile Association of India (Kaplan and Haenlein 2010). [1] Thus, in 2015, 11.000 rupees were gained from search advertizing. The telecommunication industry such as Grameenphone in Bangladesh is dependent upon big data analytics to obtain clues that can provide insights on how to acquire, increase and retain revenues from customers. A customer churn prediction project gave rise to a campaign rate of 20% as opposed to 3-5% in past campaigns, and it also led to an increase in customer incomes. This issue started to raise great concerns way back in the 1980s and 1990s and in online and blended learning research (Siegel 2013, Mayer Schonberger and Cukier 2013). [2] With the increase in the power of statistical computation over the past decades, it came to the ability of managers to find important patterns and relationships in huge datasets that would have been impossible with smaller sizes. For example, the company *Evolv* developed a predictive model that assists large global companies in making better hiring and management decisions via predictive analytics. *Evolv* crunched more than 500 million data points on issues like unemployment rates, gas prices, employment of social media, etc and it dedicated its findings to supporting customers like Xerox, AT&T and Kelly Services, to cut down on attrition by 20% by predicting at what time an employee is most likely to leave his job. Such support helps clients to witness a million of dollars of impact on their P&L (profit and loss sheet). However, while enthusiasm with the adoption of big data led to an increase in the number of advocates who strongly believe that new *vistas* of decision making would emerge (McAfee and Brynjolfsson 2012, Brown, Chui and Manyika 2011). [3] Paradoxically, the big data analytics was fraught with very serious problems that needed to be overcome before it could attain its full potential (Waterman and Hendler 2013, Boyd and Crawford 2012, Craig and Ludloff 2011). [4]

Consequently, there is a huge need to rethink big data analytics as concerns correlations with prediction, modeling and machine learning. There is a great necessity to review how we approach the conversion of big data into useful information through the interpretation of findings and analyses. As a statistical instrument, the 'fairness' of results from big data analytics is contingent upon the metrics deployed to support the model as well as its analysis and conclusions. So, while the analysis of big data is a quantitative process, in general, the underlying 'grammar' has to be developed via qualitative processes. Qualitative processes often embed subjective assumptions, prejudices and biases. In this kind of situation, statistical evidence may emerge as a self-fulfilling prophesy (O'Neil 2016). [5]

3.0 Methodology

This paper draws from Franco Moretti's (2005) [6] theory to investigate oral literature as big data. The literary historian Franco Moretti argued that in order to really comprehend literary in context, we need the aid of computers to crunch data from thousands of books at a time. This is a revolutionary approach that reflects the radical cry of Franco Moretti, who has been urging scholars to stop 'close reading' of books to tease out subtle

July 31, 2018

meanings and go for ‘distant reading’, that is, the grasping of the laws of (digital) literature, through computer-assisted crunching of thousands of texts at a time. Ever since 2010, Moretti’s Stanford Literary Lab, founded with Matthew Jockers, delivered pamphlets that chronicled its research into various topics. Eleven of the pamphlets were collected in “Canon/Archive,” and prompted a bigger question of how to circumscribe method in the field of digital humanities. Mining texts for data opens up the bigger picture. Therefore to comprehend the context where a ‘writing’ (big data is a ‘writing’) was working, distant reading marks a significant departure from traditional or ‘close’ readings. As Moretti (2000) writes in *Conjectures on World Literature*, [7] a literary study is a theological exercise, a solemn treatment of few texts taken very seriously, whereas what is needed is learning how not to ‘read’ texts as a narrow experience. Matthew Jockers, an English techie maintains that today’s literature scholar must be adept at gathering evidence not only from individual texts but equally mine digital text repositories from its context. In Jockers’ (2013) book *Macroanalysis: Digital Methods and Literary History*, [8] he uses a computer to cross-check out 700 variables across works of art, including, for example, word frequencies and the absence or presence of themes such as ‘death’.

The paper also draws from the critical paradigms of David Berry’s (2014) *Critical theory and the digital*, [9] particularly, his opposition of the *destination model* and the softwarization model of society evidenced in computational over-production and its relationship to the emerging mode of production, of augmented reality/humanity; the place of philosophy of Michel Foucault, and Gorg Lukacs’ employment of Kantian division of mental and manual labour. The play of new concepts like data-centric services, smart technologies of surveillance, new media devices, new social media, screen technologies of the e-book, collaborative work and fragmentation of hyper-temporary tasks such as Amazon’s Mechanical Turk. Insights from Thomas Allmer’s (2015) *Critical Theory and Social Media: Between Emancipation and Commodification’s* [10] dialectic of client-computer servers are deployed to illuminate the architectural power structure that underpins the online world of surveillance and control embedded in capitalist relations of production and consumption. But we also draw inspiration from his peer-to-peer model of file-sharing that allows for a common distribution and ownership of knowledge as in the Pirate Bay application.

4.0 Findings

A host of findings emerge when it comes to archiving oral literature and culture in a digital database. These have to do with when data analytics begins, the integrity of data through transcription and translation processes, how data can become a sense-making product, the state of oral literature interpretations and criticism and how to preserve the oral literature data for future generations. Thus, big data analytics is a chain-link, an expanding continuum that starts from the conceptualization of the problem in research to the collection, processing, analytics, interpretation and dissemination. Prior to the research on oral literature and culture, it is critical that the researcher should know precisely what is her research question, that is, *what is she looking for?* This then helps her to think about the methodology (the how and why) that she needs to achieve that objective. This further helps to determine how information on oral literature and culture will be processed or assembled, how data will be analyzed, the interpretation of data to decide whether one has found what one was looking for, and the final stage of dissemination and archiving in which one exposes data for a wider consumption by the public. If a researcher of oral literature does not know what he is looking for, he would not know how to assemble data in such a way that answers to what he is looking for are sought. He would equally not know how to retrieve information from the material collected and how to share insights from data with stakeholders (like the community, students, translators, etc) and preserve access to the public. From a humanistic viewpoint, ‘data analysis’ is not restricted only to scientific scholarship; it is an everyday practice. People analyze ‘data’ before they decide whether to marry someone or not, for example. They cluster, sample, assess and contrast those that they prefer based on their earlier expectations. If we consider the context of oral literature as data, the analysis of such data has to be seen as an extension of the clustering, discrimination and interpretation that we do daily in order to expand our knowledge of things. Consequently, in order for the ‘big data’ of oral literature to be archived digitally, it would require: actualization of the sound data that is embedded in electronic media like

July 31, 2018

discs and tape recorders. The audio-tape of the literature needs to be transcribed, and the video showing gestures, hand movements, facial expressions, etc need to be synchronized.

It is important to treat transcription and translation not simply as mere formalities but as critical research activities in their own right. It is important that oral literary data should be acceptable and its findings should be consistent. The oral data should show evidence of transparent and thorough collection, management and analysis. Both the original and the translation languages should be used in the software archive. The tape transcription should remain faithful to the original language of the literature. Some of the ‘big data’ questions that may arise from this academic exercise are: who should do the transcription? What challenges would the transcriber have to deal with and how should s/he deal with them? Transcription has to be consistent and systematic (Drisko 1998). [11] It can be full or partial transcription. In word for word or full transcription, an attempt is made to capture the non-verbal elements of the performed text. In partial transcription, a summary of the performance/interview may be provided or a segment of it may be identified and investigated. Transcribed texts must be based on their analytical contribution to the objective of the exercise. A partial transcription of oral literature in a software archive may lose its oral character, individuality, texture and colour. Partial transcription may prioritize the voice of the transcriber as opposed to that of the interviewee or the artist who is performing. Selective transcription tells us little about the reasons that motivated the research in the first place. It is therefore critical to attach the questions and answers to the transcription in order to clarify the motivation behind the transcription. Information about the person who transcribes, their qualifications, when he did it, how she did it, etc are big data issues. It is important that the transcriber should be a researcher because they can remember the context and are in a better position to address issues arising such as the occasionally unclear nature of taped sounds. Although it may sound economical to translate directly from homelanguage into English, French or any other language, the transcription phase should not be bypassed because the integrity of the text may be compromised. The experience of transcription is never the same as the experience of translation. Transcripts should integrate mispronunciations, ungrammatical errors, non-verbal texts, elisions, and background noises. Although, it is not a good thing to essentialize transcriptions, the golden rule is to narrow the gap between the actual performance of the oral text and its fossilized and frozen version on print. The transcription should integrate the transcriber’s profile, his age, educational level, gender, ethnic/faith background and so on. This will enable the analyst to appreciate how well the transcriber can slip from one source language of the text to the target language (Rossman and Rallis). [12]

When it comes to free translation, the translator has to make certain that he does not impose meaning that is not contained in the original oral literary text. Quotations should be read well to avoid misrepresentation of meaning (Rubin and Bennett 1986, Pellegrini et al 1984, Rubin et al 2000, Rubin 1995). [13] In the event of employment of an interpreter, care must be taken to ensure that there are no communication gaps. There are always challenges because of the interpreter’s effect on the informant, the translation process and the translation in terms of words, perspective, etc. Thus, a debate on conceptual issues can be started in order to clarify these points between researcher and translator. Translation-related challenges are dependent upon the skills, effort and time put in by the translator. If the researcher is also the translator, then the challenge would be contingent upon factors like their autobiography, fluency in the language, knowledge of the language, etc. Other intervening factors would include the relationship between the translator and the researcher, his competence, material circumstances, etc. If he is not competent, he may translate from Lamnso’ to English as: M’ nÔ namă = I am smoking a cigarette. A competent translator would translate as: M’ nÔ namă = I drink^x tobacco. He can attach a footnote to explain ‘drink’ as ‘smoke’.

In functional translation, the translator translates with the practical needs of the researcher in focus such as content and style to the detriment of structure, for example (Wasamba 2009). [14] Various aspects of performance such as facial gestures, interjections, bodily movements, etc may be left out. Even the tonal and intonational qualities may hardly be translated. In this way, even with the best of intentions and skills, poor video and audio recording may compromise the process of transcription, translation and analysis of the big data of orality.

5.0 Discussions

There is no doubt that big data analytics has a value that can be utilized, for example, to generate an archival software system of efficiency for the oral culture. Big data analytics in culture needs to correlate text with the context in order to facilitate collaborative and group work. Leadership in the big data oral culture should exploit insights from the text-context continuum to make strategic decisions. This was the insight that was deployed, for example, by the Obama for America campaign team when they applied their digital-content continuum. The team (A/B) tested multiple versions not only of its email requests (text) for contributions during the US presidential election period but also discovered that content (context) is the most important issue to deal with in email advertising. This is so because online users were more likely to open their email ads on condition that they started the subject matter with the friendly attention getting call ‘hey’. The campaign raised more than a billion dollars thanks not only to the integration of direct marketing, micro targeting and market research, but also thanks to messages tailored to the needs of individuals. Similarly, almost every big business today employs big data analytics by going beyond software technology to market research; for example, Microsoft acquired Nokia thanks not only to big data analytics of the market but also of its environment (Aluya 2014 : 221). [15] The deployment of the text-context continuum may take other forms. In 2008, the senior editor of *Fortune*, Betsy Morris, cited Steve Jobs of Apple Inc., as declaring that: ‘we do no market research’ (as text), as a way of justifying big data humanistic practices in business like development of products through *intuition* (as context) without implying that software insights from market demand were exploited alone. But a lawsuit later showed that Apple Inc. market research was also exploiting environmental or intuitive insights from computerized big data analytics. Big data analytics in software involves the collection and deployment of data to facilitate comprehension of the ‘likes’ and ‘dislikes’ of customers of Apple Inc., for example. Apple Inc.’s success is therefore partly thanks to big data analytics. Steve Jobs, the co-founder and chair of Apple, Inc. attempted to activate digital decision-making as a self-regulating area of discretion by declaring as he asserted, so that he may be perceived as a prophet of entrepreneurship, disorientate his competitors or keep the advantage gleaned from analytics to himself. Other aspirant technology managers, following his footsteps, developed products/services without referring to the digital resources of market demand and by drawing chiefly from their *sense* of what prospective customers would request rather than by probing into the statistics of customers themselves.

Although data types are often interconnected in an *explicit* or *tacit* manner, they present with different facilities for human comprehension and machine *interpretation*. As a result of these variations, serious difficulties emerge when data that was accumulated over several days, weeks, months or years, have to be analyzed in significant ways in order to make adequate decisions for a future context that is changing all the time. In such contexts of complexity, insights cannot be mined from data by manual analysis and inspection from a single source; rather, data has to be investigated by comprehending and identifying patterns, and aggregating appropriate data volumes from a number of sources. The challenge here is essentially one of researching the tacit pathologies of big data: how should tools be *designed*, for example, to handle the ways data is structured for the query, analysis, etc. In such critical settings, technologies deployed in big data analytics remain technologies and do not give us much clue as to what the data *signifies*. If data itself cannot be *signified*, one cannot make sense of big data and therefore one cannot make relevant discoveries that can assist one to make correct decisions capable of generating productive outcomes. Consequently, it is critical to deploy human intelligence to address problems in such fluid situations by capturing discourse from which one can extract insights capable of assisting machines to deal with challenges in complex contexts.

This paper raises the problematical issue of how *changing* (from explicit to tacit) context may impact ‘negatively’ on decision making in big data analytics if the software environment of the humanities is ignored. An adequate investigation into the database of oral literature can only be significant when the collection of data is methodologically grounded and theoretically informed. Research work in software archives hardly documents *how* data were collected, classified, organized and analyzed. What is often missing in the scholarship is the

July 31, 2018

framework that enables researchers to illuminate readers to see what they saw in data. The common practice in fieldwork consists of transcribing, translating and publishing books that are submitted as the oral literature of a given person. But it is not enough to present data as work without explaining the process that led to it or *how* the data was acquired. Readers are not necessarily observing what fieldworkers are doing, the processes taking place before, during and after the collection of data. The absence of such information can impede the analysis of data, and can lead to doubts about the integrity of data and conclusions arrived at in a study. Data analysis is embedded in research methods because it is only when it is clear how a *text* stands in relation to its *performance* and when its performance is related to its tradition, that the real task of analysis of data content can start (Vansina 1985, Tonkin 1986). [16] The analysis of oral data cannot be disembedded from the process of, for example, interviewing informants (Abrams 2010). [17] As Edwards and Walcott (1996) [18] argue there is merit in a research setting where there are questions and answers and there are a willingness and openness to make what one is looking for explicit.

In elucidation of the digital equation and its *humanities* side, there is no doubt that it is self explanatory why it is so difficult to persuade a manager to make a *decision* in favour of utilizing ICT technology resources when, for example, the latter *believe* that they understand their customers best through past intuitive experiences and prediction failures and when they are afraid that ICT technology may take away their creative freedom or instinctive power. Decision making in the deployment of big data analytics, is therefore confronted with multiple challenges of the *spontaneity* of context. In order to address these challenges, this paper suggests that certain ‘discursive practices’ that computers and algorithmic formulas cannot handle efficiently and need to be assisted with the need to be identified.

In the case of decision-making for the use of big data analytics in cognitively complex and data intensive contexts like the Dicode Project, new strategies to deal effectively with challenges of big data correlation were deployed such as email testing, social media analytics, etc. When the *Dicode* project was set up, its objectives were to facilitate and increase collaboration and decision making in contexts that are cognitively complex and where data was intensively exploited (Karacapidilis 2014, *Mastering data intensive collaboration and decision-making: research and practical applications in the dicode project*). [19] In order to realize these objectives, the project constructed high performance computing paradigms with its data processing technologies capable of significantly searching, analyzing and aggregating data derived from sources that are very large, diverse and evolving. But what marked out this project was that a lot of stress was placed on deepening *insights* on big data exploitation and on questions of *cooperation* and *sense making*. The project amalgamated the reasoning capabilities of both machine and man by incorporating interoperable services that were capable of minimizing overloads in data complexity and intensity to manageable levels in critical decision-making contexts. Stakeholders were capacitated to be more effective and more productive in their practices. Dicode project services were released under an open sourced licence. Thanks to the Dicode project, certain use cases were authenticated, namely, the trial of clinical treatment effects, clinico-genomic research assimilator and the mining of opinion from unstructured Web 2.0 data. Dicode services were validated for the automated analysis of large amounts of unstructured Web data existing in the social media cyberspace. By spidering data from social media sites that were popular, it was now possible to use APIs from various Web 2.0 platforms. By broadening out clinical trials in clinico-genomic research beyond just rheumatoid arthritis, for example, it was now possible to facilitate the process of making decisions in clinical and drug trials thanks to the combination of datasets obtained from clinical results of patients such as physical examination and blood tests and scan modalities such as dynamic/static MRI scan images, x-rays, etc to explore drug efficiency and effectivity in a given trial. The Dicode project validated the need to evaluate, explore, disseminate and diffuse scientific results and findings in profoundly collaborative ways. A use case was elaborated that integrated clinico-genomic knowledge discovery and decision-making based on *tacit* (rather than only explicit) processes of targeting the identification and validation of predictive biomarkers and clinico-genomic models.

Thanks to the evolutionary method, the Dicode project objectives were met by actively engaging different stakeholders such as technical partners and user case agents in the design, specification and assessment of

July 31, 2018

envisaged technological solutions. By incrementing developments, end users were able to test Dicode project services right from its primitive to its maturity stages. For example, the operational prototypes of the services were made available at the first second and third years of the project. User requirements were continuously refined through testing processes that involved users in all cases. The project was sustained by maintaining an operational suite of services that facilitated proof-of-concept purposes, various trial platforms and enabling various dissemination, diffusion and exploitation activities. At the commencement stage, the Dicode project's scientific and technical objectives were designed to comprehend current practices and needs of organizations and communities as far as the exploitation of intensive data and its collaborative contexts of complex cognitions and decision making were concerned. Use cases were represented and elaborated throughout the project and related settings with their needs and practices were considered so as to show how they associated with large data-sets and real-time data. This schema of foundational layout, integration, validation, enrichment and broadening was able to be applied to a wide variety of areas. Feedback was obtained from the evaluation of Dicode services across the use cases, followed by an analysis of lessons learned and revision of service's specifications so as to knowledgeably inform iteration. By facilitating collaboration between end users and technical partners, a more profound understanding was acquired of the similarities and differences between use cases and the exploration of Dicode services and their potentials.

By facilitating and enhancing collaboration, enriching sense making and promoting a healthy ground for decision making in cognitively complex and data intensive settings, the Dicode project was able to expose a suite of interoperable, adaptive and innovative services that satisfied a range of requirements from conceptual to technical levels. In this way, Dicode services captured, delivered and analyzed relevant information and knowledge online and emphasized adaptability to user requirement shifts and changes in operating conditionalities. Usability issues were addressed in the third year of the project and this concerned development of data pre-processing, data acquisition and data mining services. Before raw data was stored to address the foreseen solution, it was efficiently manipulated. In this light, services included paying more focused attention to the diversity of data sources and formats, so that tractable information captured was purposeful. Web resources, social media APIs and third party feeds were carefully integrated. The services included transforming a variety of documents into their canonical formats, structuring documents from their layout information by detecting abstracts, navigation and commentaries, cleansing of data by removing worthless database records, discarding 'noises' from webpages, and performing linguistic annotations and language detection functions. Dicode services that mine data by exploiting and constructing on cloud infrastructure and other data processing technologies provide classification and clustering, high performance full text search, filtering and fusion of directed data, indexing of data, and data aggregation that is meaningful. Other text mining technologies that are advanced include opinion and relation extraction, named entity recognition, and so forth that aid in extracting valuable semantic information from texts that are unstructured. Data mining also integrates the deployment of intelligent technologies like similarity learning and local pattern mining and derivations.

Among Dicode's target groups, one can identify public services, public health and e-science in the public sector, media and medicine as well as advertisement and communication in the private sector. Service development, service integration and consultancy services are in the IT industry. The Dicode solution is user friendly and is constructed on the machine-human intelligence synergy. Its platform is open to sourcing of information from external data providers and to additional applications and modules of external developers tailored to changing market contexts. This increases the user's creativity and productivity. End users become the real evaluators of the Dicode platform. Its framework is accepted by users outside the Dicode consortium and its *value* is acknowledged by communities and groups. Its relationship with business and scientific stakeholders, workshops and diffusion activities are relevant to the market. Its framework is portable and adaptable in a wide range of domains, academia and industries. The high performance of the scalable data mining in cloud computing has shown added value in the added value of the Dicode framework. The Dicode framework leverages skills, improves the quantity and quality of output and reduces costs and time thanks to the

July 31, 2018

aggregation and integration of various stakeholders' perspectives across different collaborative decision making activities. It opens up to new working practices of cognitively complex and data intensive contexts.

The use of analytics has been very effective because of testing experimentations. When the Obama for America Campaign Team launched Barack Obama's bid for the 2012 presidential elections (Clayton, 2016, *The presidential campaign of Barack Obama: : A critical analysis of a racially transcendent strategy*), [20] they tested *alternative versions of all its email solicitations* designed to mobilize contributions. From the investigations, they discovered that one of the important things to test in email advertising is the subject matter or *content*. Whenever the content was not interesting, the email was not opened. When the subject matter was exciting, and the subject 'Hey' was efficiently impactful and responsive, they were employed in later email ads. Thus, an integrated approach to analytics that combined direct response marketing with micro-targeting, was a strategy that generated a billion USD. The strategy of market research and campaign methods concentrated on tailoring messages to individual preferences and tastes. Demonstrations show that analytics outperforms intuition. For example, alternative ads can be tested for one's work in order to predict outcomes. One can find examples of ads with test results (in Which Test Won at <https://whichtestwon.com/>) and when presented with about ten alternative ads, one can pick out the version that worked out best. By recording the answers and comparing the predictions to actual test results, one would be able to show that the flip of a coin is a better predictor of customer behaviour than intuition. Apple Inc., for example, collects and utilizes data not only from the 'likes' but also from the 'dislikes of customers'. The insurance industry in India leverages big data analytics thanks to the development of the probability theory in mathematics. Its value rose to 66 billion USD in 2013 as reported by the India Brand Equity Foundation. In the context of digital marketing, the Internet and Mobile Association of India revealed that 30% of India's digital advertising market deployed *search advertising*, which is a major text analytics application. For 2015, the value of search advertising was put at 11000 crore rupees. What accounts for the high competition of the telecommunication sector is that providers get clues from analytics in order to acquire, retain and increase incomes from customers. The most important Bangladeshi company in telecommunications called Grameenphone reported that thanks to a customer churn prediction project, they were able to carry out a campaign that showed a take-up rate of 20 percent which differed from the 3/5 percentage in earlier campaigns. This project also augmented customer revenue.

In order to provide insights into organizational big data decision-making, social media has emerged as a new tool that facilitates the process of decision-making. In this way, decision-making can be enhanced by drawing critical views from the ways users generate social media content by sharing experiences, opinions, and knowledge on multiple questions. The employment of social media creates huge quantities of data that have great potential to enlighten decision-makers in organizations. Decision making in big data analytics cannot be an isolated sphere on its own but needs input from social media because social media-generated data may impact the perceptions, attitudes and choices of consumers in positive or negative ways. Thus, social media can be deployed by organizations as a low cost marketing channel to improve their engagement with customers as well as ameliorate customer awareness of their products, brands and services. In social media analytics, data is stored, analyzed and interpreted for the insights they may bring forth to decision-makers. Through different techniques such as text mining, these insights can be used to derive benefits to firms. Organizations need an 'intimate' method such as social media analytics to relate to customers, comprehend and mould their perception of products, brands and services. With this platform, its tools and techniques, organizations can be enabled to identify key influencers, provide more responsive customer service, target market campaigns and analyse feelings of customers. Despite the fact that many organizations invest in social media analytics, few can be considered as effective adopters.

This next section of the paper presents a discursive framework model of the Social media analytics (SMA) that can achieve benefits based on *motivations*, *resource-based view* and *dynamics capabilities*. SMA can be defined as a group of internet-based applications that are building on the foundations of Web 2.0. SMA examples include Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, social news sites, online reviews, virtual communities and blogs (Chamlertwat, Bhattarakosol, Rungkasiri, and Haruechaiyasak, 2012). [21] Because of the large number of

July 31, 2018

about 850 million active users on Facebook, for example, and the time spent in the US alone which increased by 37% to 121 billion minutes in 2012, the employment of social media created huge amounts of data on consumer opinions, sentiments toward products/services and experiences of brands, which can be of great potential value to business. Thanks to the deployment of analytics-based capabilities, one can interpret and analyze vast chunks of semi-structured and unstructured data from these social media analytics sources. The use of social media analytics enables us to provide insights to businesses with respect to customer *sentiments, values, opinions* and *perspectives* on new *products/services*, and *brands* (Acerbi 2016), [22] Social media analytics presents opportunities for organizations to signify the market as a new kind of ‘conversation’ between customers and organizations and this departs from the traditional business-to-consumer approach to business that prioritizes a one-way type of communication (Larson and Watson, 2011). [23] It is necessary to explain how businesses can gain benefits from social media analytics. Companies are increasingly investing in social media analytics technologies in order to comprehend customers' and customers' perception of their market positions and brands. The deployment of social media analytics can empower businesses to attain their clients with a large scale and very low cost. Social media analytics provides organizations with an improved means of connecting with customers and comprehending/shaping of products/services and brands. The tools and techniques employed can enable organizations to target market campaigns, make available more responsive customer service, analyze sentiments of customers, and identify sources of influences. Social media analytics returns cannot be measured only in terms of classical financial indicators, but also in the ‘big’ light of customer behaviours and perceptions, motivations, etc. In social media analytics, decision making intersects with organizational *motivations* as well. By organizational motivations, we are referring to the goals that an organization pursues and that subsequently orientate its actions. By intersecting decision making and social media analytics, one can make informed decisions that are generated from the *monitoring* of customer interactions; decisions informed by *analysis* of such interactions and one can also *influence* such interactions on social media platforms. Organizations would be motivated to decide in favour of deploying social media because they can also offer a platform for *persuasion, awareness* and *collaboration*. The platform enables the analyst to ‘*listen*’ to conversations of customers, uncover new ideas on *sentiments, topics* and *participants*, fragment the market into those who are *backing out*, those *who influence*, those who may become *potential customers*, and so forth. Other insights on sentiments, associations, feelings, opinions, etc may be embedded in decision making processes in organizations. For example, on the basis of such insights, an organization may decide to plan out a marketing campaign by employing media channels.

In the spirit of ‘big data’ in social media, the concept of *awareness* can be ‘exploded’ even further into *issues* of the customer’s environment, customer’s *values* and *behaviours*, the *efficiency* of online marketing campaigns, new *ideas* for brand reputation and engagement, *feedback* from online initiatives and so forth. This kind of explosion would enable one to analyze adverse events, evaluate effectiveness and return on investment on marketing and initiatives, and track out levels of competition. Social media analytics *persuasion*, which is the collection and investigation of data in order to promote advertising, marketing and sales, has to do with the promotion of products/services, brands, identification of social influencers in order to enable marketing through ‘word of mouth’ and increase sales. It is not only the identification of social media *channels* that is important, but also the promotion of sales initiatives as well as the generation of sales leads. Decision making in the context of social media motivation, signifies that organizations adopt and use ICT resources like data warehouses, infrastructure, tools (e.g. Hadoop, social network analysis, etc) that can provide *text* and *sentiment analyses*. In the context of social media analytics, competencies engage not only with skills in individuals and teams that accomplish tasks in organizations, it also signifies competences in business, ICT and management, *insights* from other organizational systems and harnessing of those insights so that they are relevant and aligned to business (marketing, sales) strategies. Social media analytics competencies go beyond the management of structured data sets to incorporate *unstructured data sets, text mining, language processing, social network analysis* and *sentiment analysis*. It also engages with the management of unstructured data sets, Decision making intersects with social media analytics practices, that is, the means by which organizations take action,

July 31, 2018

the mechanism used to store and access knowledge on how one realizes these actions. Practices help people to develop competences in particular ways of working and attaining objectives. Practices are often routinized to such an extent that they become reliable and are named as 'best practices'. The practice in *Starbucks*, for example, consists in the employment of competences within brand management, sales lead generation and campaign planning. Social media analytics capabilities empowers organizations to collect insights from customers, access digital marketing campaigns and discover new ideas through *sentiment analysis*, behavioural sentiments, sentiment polarity, text mining and web analytics: (customer behavior, preference and intention), and real-time intelligence (usage of products, revenue growth, market success, brand mentions),

In social media analytics, the goals are to gather insights from customers, evaluate digital marketing campaigns, discover new ideas, identify social influencers, and identify popular social media channels. The capabilities include *sentiment analysis* through polarity of sentiments, behaviour of sentiments; *text mining and web analytics* through customer behaviour, preference and intention, *real-time intelligence* via the usage of products, revenue growth, market success, brand mentions, additional capacities include *trend analysis and crowd intelligence*: from new insights and innovation, products/services, *weak signal analysis* through early emerging trends, *analysis of competition* by tracking competitive products/services and brands, *analysis of influence* through identification of influencers for marketing and sales. *Social network analysis* is done to map out the relationship between online communities and users, *data mining and machine learning* to identify popular purchases and construct smart wish lists, prescriptions or recommendations. By *optimizing the channels and propensity of modeling*, one can identify profitable social media platforms and models that influence purchase decisions. By intersecting decision making and social media analytics insights, one can transform practices into profit generation, especially through customer management, performance management and process management. As customer management, decision making signifies that one understands the preferences and expectations of a customer base and the characteristics of its market. Social media analytics provides market intelligence for customer management. An organization must be able to attain flexibility, cost economies and speed thanks to the effective design and management of its key processes. Social media analytics can thus provide the relevant insights necessary to empower key business processes and enlighten stakeholders about the value of social media analytics data in organizations. Social media analytics can inform performance management with insights so that an organization can design and manage its systems of measurement and monitoring of performance, therefore supporting managerial decision making on the communication of performance to stakeholders. This way, managers can justify the return on investment of social media analytics. A good decision making process intersects with strategic management in information systems deployed to comprehend and explain ways in which investments in information systems result in organizational benefits and competitive advantage. A good decision making process envisages an organization as an assortment of valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable *resources* that facilitate competition and success such as *software, hardware, data, people* and *capabilities* (such as skills) and routine *practices*. Decision-making has to align itself to the prospect of ICT potentialising business value and to impact directly or indirectly. A company has to perform: but prior to its possibilities of performance, decisions must be made on certain pre-conditions that must be met such as business units, processes and initiatives, which are by the way linked to various forms of benefits. However, before benefits are achieved, decision making must consider not only the efficiency and effectiveness of resources but also the 'bigger picture' of the volatility of the business environment through dynamic capabilities. Decision making has to renew and configure the resource base of an organization by exploring dynamic capabilities such as *new skills* and *new practices* within the context of changing technologies.

Thanks to dynamic capacities, a mechanism can be provided for social media analytics resources to be reconfigured and renewed. This capacity is very critical in volatile contexts of business. IT and social media analytics capabilities are first order constructs, while dynamic capacities are second order constructs. Dynamic capacities are comprised of routines for *searching* for new opportunities, *selecting* and funding these opportunities with the potential to offer benefits to an organization and of course, *asset orchestration* that can

July 31, 2018

renew IT and social media analytics. Dynamic capacities can therefore identify new business opportunities, and integrate new IT and social media analytics into existing organizational practices. In this way, social media analytics motivations can lead to the adoption, development and employment of social media analytics resources that can in turn lead to organizational benefits in terms of customership, financial and organizational effectiveness benefits. Social media analytics benefits can be exploded in terms of financial (*costs, revenue, improved profits*), behavioural (*use of insights of the resources*), perceptual (customer satisfaction), customer (*increased understanding and engagement, improved satisfaction, improved service, comprehending customer sentiments about products/services and brands, customer trends, issues, etc*). Organizational benefits can be exploded into higher levels of innovation (through crowdsourcing about products/services), reduced market time, improved flexibility in production/supply chain management, improved marketing campaign, reduced costs for brand promotion (through SM platforms like blogs, Twitter).

The benefits of social media analytics can be multiple. By gathering customer insights via sentiment analysis, text mining and web analysis using the Twitter platform, one can improve customer understanding, customer engagement, and customer service. By assessing online marketing campaigns via real-time market intelligence, one can improved market strategy, and gain insights about target markets/activities. By discovering new ideas via analysis of trends and crowd intelligence, analysis of weak signals, analysis of competitors using the Twitter platform on a brand, it is possible to improve predictive modeling and business planning, and increase new businesses. By drawing from techniques of persuasion to identify social influencers via influence analysis and social network analysis, one can increase the customer base and better manage brand reputation. The identification of popular social media channels, via machine learning, and data mining, optimization of channel and propensity modelling can result in the generation of increased sales leads through conversion rates, social e-commerce sales, click rates, etc.

Big data analytics can guide excellent decisions in business or in politics but tacit insights can make such decisions sustainable in the long run. Even when business managers rant about their use of analytics, they quietly exploit *intuition* to arrive at good decision-making from behind the scenes. But there are serious hurdles to the general application of software data analytics in industries and businesses. Software decision making in big data analytics is confronted with multiple challenges in different contexts. By ‘context’, we are referring not only to *space*, and *time*, but also to the *agency*, which is elements of humanism in big data analytics. When it comes to ‘agency’, there is still a strong *belief* and confidence among managers and business leaders that their intuitive understanding of customers’ needs has more potential than the capacity of machines to learn and analyze algorithms. This culture of intuition grew from the centenarian practice of direct response marketing, that involved selling directly to the customer. They knew intuitively by testing alternative ads and evaluating the outcomes. In addition, there is a tendency to rationalize prediction breakdowns with the benefit of hindsight and from past experiences; there is also a certain apprehension that machines may appropriate their freedom and power to create. The tendency to see big data analytics as just another ordinary business project can be reversed not by simply making requests for finance but by constructing a convincing protocol for the investment. The protocol should tread the fine line between costs and benefits. Costs are very easy to define because one already knows the products and services one is offering and what they cost. One can also evaluate internal costs such as overheads and compensation of personnel. But, on the other hand, benefits have to do with either income increases or cost decreases. There is unlimited potential to increase business income and so it is tempting to draw the attention of business leaders who are wary of promises to increase revenue. Consequently, the second option of reduction of costs through big data analytics may be necessary to introduce the analytics gradually. One can start off with small resourced projects so as to secure the funding necessary for larger ones. A low-risk project in which the business leader’s language is employed and the definition of objectives/findings aligned with his duties would be prerequisites for building trust and prospects of deciding in favour of the deployment of the analytics. The existence of big data increases the hunt for exciting correlations; however, correlation, itself does not establish causality. Causality requires models and theories, but they have clear limitations in their capacity to predict the future. So, it is one thing to create correlations, and still another thing

July 31, 2018

to shift from correlations to causal attributes. When it comes to enormously complex problems, classical causal science ends up being ineffective because data sets are very large and the scale of the problem increases.

Today, the collaborative setting of decision making in big data analytics is marked by very large and increasing volumes of data of multiple types, from diverse sources with low signal-to-noise ratio and other variations like importance, subjectivity, etc (individual evaluations, measurements, opinions, scientific results, etc). But serious problems start to emerge when a manager has to consider the exploitation of data volumes collected weeks or months before and she has to analyze them meaningfully in order to make decisions. When datasets are complex, it is necessary to identify, comprehend and exploit data patterns, to aggregate data volumes from different sources, and mine them in ways that cannot be done with manual inspection and analysis. It is also a challenge to structure out data for queries and to design tools that will process them effectively. But in this kind of setting, big data analytics is incapable of providing insight into the *meaning* of data. In order to make better decisions, one must determine the sense in big data and make discoveries; human intelligence must be nurtured and captured to extract insights and help machines to deal with complex situations. (Fred, Ana, et al 2015). [24]

Big data analytics provides the contextual background from which a good decision making act can be leveraged whether in the computer software or in the archiving of oral literature and culture. Decision making is not merely a self-governing act of computer users; it is also a construction of big data analytics, which should be implemented thoughtfully. Big data analytics has value but it also needs decision making because the process of merely analyzing data does not result in the production of value and profit. The efforts that are put into the collection of data can only commence yielding fruits when their analysis leads to information that can be actionated. Nevertheless, big data analytics and decision making are confronted with certain challenges. It is not enough to analyze data and connect it to the decision making. One has to identify critical business problems, construct an understanding of a wide range of possible corrective acts and emerge with appropriate analyses of directions that can determine the most appropriate action to take in context. It is important that one should prepare, re-present and defend the case for business analytics and convey results convincingly.

Even more formidable is the challenge of how to build a business case for analytics. A technology research firm called Gartner Inc wrote a report in 2012 in which it was discovered that 20% of all IT projects with budgets fell below 350,000 USD and when the budget of the project increased, the failure rate also augmented. The managers of the projects were reluctant to consider analytics as to the way forward. Consequently, in order to prepare a business case, one has to delineate two major factors, namely, costs and profit. Costs have to do with outlining the products/services one desires and what they cost, internal costs such as staff and overheads, etc. On the other hand, profit takes the form of revenue increases and cost decreases. The potential to augment profit increases is very high but the problem is that managers are not comfortable with revenue increases; they prefer reduction of cost projects because outcomes of analytics projects are often difficult to prove, and the one in charge may not have the authority to effect changes in their businesses necessary for income increases. Hence, there is a need to emphasize the definition of appropriate technical terms, precision and accuracy of a model the data analyst is proposing, choice of appropriate tests and so forth. In order to persuade business executives, the analyst has to employ an appropriate financial language with respect to money (for example, Euros, Dollars, etc, percentage of sales increase, customer churn rates, conversion rates, instead of statistical data). One has to be brief by presenting the most important information, minimize details and reveal specifics gradually.

In order for decision-making to be efficient as far as the data-driven model of a company is concerned, an organization has to access substantial and relevant data from a range of activities, but, in most companies big data sets are hard to come by. Even when companies have enough data, the next decision making problem they have to deal with emerges because computers and algorithms are unable to consider variables such as *changing weather, shifting moods, and the dynamism of relationships*, when anticipating human behaviour. These are variables that might influence patterns of customers purchasing products. Another major variable is the factor of *time* which also plays a role in how well technologies work. Although a model may be successful at a given

July 31, 2018

point in time, customer behaviour may undergo such profound changes with time to the extent that, to be effective, the model has to be updated. For example, the 2008/9 financial crisis showed how important consideration to the variable of time could be because invalid models were predicting the likelihood of mortgage customers repaying loans without taking into account the possibility that housing prices might fall. A thoroughly critical understanding of predictive analytics can facilitate business forecasting, and thus empower us to make wiser decisions on when to and when not to apply predictive methods into digital technology management planning.

6.0 Conclusion

Decision making in big data analytics is a very complex act and is an ephemeral process utilized in all (e-) businesses and in virtually every other domain of human endeavour, but it needs to draw insights from tacit knowledge in the archiving of oral literature and culture and in every other business or political endeavour. The status of decision making takes different forms depending on changes in cognitively discursive, complex and intensive contexts and in very significant ways, for example, from one (small, medium-sized, big) enterprise to another. As a result, it is very difficult to make a persuasive case for the value of analytics and its benefits for business/industry, etc, in the face of a decision making act/process by a manager when it is prone to ambiguity, skepticism, resistance, etc (Kane, Gerald C. Jerry, et al 2014, Kiron, Palmer, Philips and Krushwitz 2012). [25] People tend to lack confidence in their own comprehension of the consumer; they employ hindsight to rationalize failures in past predictions and they develop fears over concerns that their creative powers may erode with the adoption of analytics (Kulkarni et al. 2016). Decision making may be overridden by *intuition* in the domain of market research; for example, decision making in the company Apple, Inc., was marked by the deployment of visionary insights. Decision-making (whether taken with enthusiasm, skepticism, resistance) is a discrete act, a mental process restricted to the sphere of *desire* and therefore cannot generate value, competitiveness and certitude on its own terms, however, intuitive.

Works Cited

- i. Kaplan, Andreas M., and Michael Haenlein. "Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media." *Business horizons* 53.1 (2010): 59-68.
- ii. Siegel, Eric. *Predictive Analytics: The Power to Predict Who Will Click, Buy, Lie, or Die*. London: John Wiley & Sons, 2013.
- iii. Cukier, Kenneth, and Viktor Mayer-Schonberger. "Big Data: A Revolution That Will Transform How We Live." *Work and Think*, London: John Murray (2013).
- iv. McAfee, Andrew, et al. "Big data: the management revolution." *Harvard Business Review* 90.10 (2012): 60-68.
- v. Brown, Brad, Michael Chui, and James Manyika. "Are you ready for the era of 'big data'." *McKinsey Quarterly* 4.1 (2011): 24-35.
- vi. Waterman, K. Krasnow, and Jim Hendler. "Getting the Dirt on Big Data." *Big Data* 1.3 (2013): 137-140.
- vii. Craig, Terence, and Mary E. Ludloff. *Privacy and Big Data: The Players, Regulators, and Stakeholders*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc., 2011.
- viii. O'neil, Cathy. *Weapons of Math Destruction: How Big Data Increases Inequality And Threatens Democracy*. London: Broadway Books, 2016.
- ix. Moretti, Franco. *Graphs, Maps, Trees: Abstract Models for a Literary History*. Verso, 2005.
- x. Moretti, Franco. "Conjectures On World Literature." *New Left Review* (2000): 54-68.
- xi. Jockers, Matthew L. *Macroanalysis: Digital Methods and Literary History*. Illinois: University of Illinois Press, 2013.

July 31, 2018

- xii. Berry, David M. *Critical Theory and the Digital*. Bloomsbury Publishing USA, 2015.
- xiii. Schaefer, Peter. "David M Berry, *Critical theory and the digital*. Bloomsbury Publishing: New York, 2014; 260 pp.; ISBN: 1441166394, \$120.00 (hbk)." (2016): 5.
- xiv. Allmer, Thomas. *Critical Theory And Social Media: Between Emancipation And Commodification*. Routledge, London 2015.
- xv. Drisko, James W. "Using Qualitative Data Analysis Software." *Computers in Human Services* 15.1 (1998): 1-19.
- xvi. Rallis, Sharon F., and Gretchen B. Rossman. "Mixed Methods In Evaluation Contexts: A Pragmatic Framework." *Handbook of Mixed Methods In Social And Behavioral Research* (2003): 491-512.
- xvii. Rubin, Donald L., and Bennett A. Rafoth. "Oral Language Criteria For Selecting Listenable Materials: An Update For Reading Teachers And Specialists." *Reading Psychology: An International Quarterly* 7.3 (1986): 137-151.
- xviii. Pellegrini, A. D., Lee Galda, and Donald L. Rubin. "Context in text: The development of oral and written language in two genres." *Child Development* (1984): 1549-1555.
- xix. Rubin, Donald L., Teresa Hafer, and Kevin Arata. "Reading and listening to oral-based versus literate-based discourse." *Communication Education* 49.2 (2000): 121-133.
- xx. Rubin, David C. *Memory in Oral Traditions: The Cognitive Psychology Of Epic, Ballads, And Counting-Out Rhymes*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1995.
- xxi. Wasamba, Peter. "Going beyond data collection in ethnography: Options for bridging the gap between researchers and archivists." *International Journal of African Renaissance Studies-Multi-, Inter-and Transdisciplinarity* 7.2 (2012): 4-17.
- xxii. Joseph Aluya, D. B. A. *The Influences of Big Data Analytics*. Author House, 2014.
- xxiii. Vansina, Jan M. *Oral Tradition As History*. Univ of Wisconsin Press, Wisconsin, 1985.
- xxiv. Tonkin, Elizabeth. "Investigating oral tradition." *The Journal of African History* 27.2 (1986): 203-213.
- xxv. Abrams, Lynn. *Oral History Theory*. Routledge, London, 2010.
- xxvi. Edwards, Norval, and Derek Walcott. "Derek Walcott: The Poetics of Two Margins." *Mississippi Review* 24.3 (1996): 12-35.
- xxvii. Karacapilidis, Nikos, ed. *Mastering Data-intensive Collaboration and Decision Making: Research and Practical Applications in the Dicode Project*. Vol. 5. Springer Science & Business Media, 2014.
- xxviii. Clayton, Dewey M. *The Presidential Campaign of Barack Obama: A Critical Analysis of a Racially Transcendent Strategy*. Routledge, London, 2010.
- xxix. Chamlerwat, Wilas, et al. "Discovering Consumer Insight from Twitter via Sentiment Analysis." *J. UCS* 18.8 (2012): 973-992.
- xxx. Acerbi, Alberto. "A Cultural Evolution Approach To Digital Media." *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience* 10 (2016): 636.
- xxxi. Larson, Keri, and Richard Watson. "The value of social media: toward measuring social media strategies." (2011).
- xxxii. Fred, Ana, et al., eds. *Knowledge Discovery, Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management: 6th International Joint Conference, IC3K 2014, Rome, Italy, October 21-24, 2014, Revised Selected Papers*. Vol. 553. Springer, 2015.
- xxxiii. Kane, Gerald C. Jerry, et al. "Moving beyond marketing: Generating social business value across the enterprise." *MIT Sloan Management Review* 56.1 (2014): 1.

July 31, 2018

xxxiv. Kiron, David, et al. "What managers really think about social business." *MIT Sloan Management Review* 53.4 (2012): 51.

xxxv. Kulkarni, Parag, Sarang Joshi, and Meta S. Brown. *Big data analytics*. PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd., 2016.
<https://books.google.com/books?isbn=8120351169>

Sketch bio

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